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Correlation Between Digital Literacy and Critical Thinking skills among Undergraduate Students in Delta State University, Abraka

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Abstract

The study investigated correlation between digital literacy and critical thinking skills among undergraduate students of Delta State University Abraka. One research question and one hypothesis were developed to guide the investigation. The study's population consisted of 1,020 students from Delta State University Abraka' computer science and business education departments. The study's sample size was 102 students from Delta State University in Abraka. The data collection instrument was a structured questionnaire titled Digital Literacy and its Correlation with Critical Thinking among University Students (DLCCTASUA). The questionnaire consisted of 20 items divided into two halves. portion A contained personal information, whereas portion B had the 20 items. The objects were placed on a four-point rating system. The Cronbach Alpha reliability was used to determine the consistency of the instrument which provided reliability co-efficient of 0.98, indicating that the instrument was reliable. Mean and standard deviation was used to analyze the research question for the study at 2.50. Indicating that if the calculated mean value is more than 2.50 accept but if it is less than the 2.50 reject. Regression was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05. significant level. Indicating that if the observed p-value is less than the fixed p-value, accept otherwise reject. The finding among others shown that there is significant weak relationship between digital literacy and critical thinking among students in Delta State University Abraka. It was recommended from the finding that universities should teach students on the use digital in learning.

Keywords: Digital literacy, critical thinking, university Students

INTRODUCTION

Digital literacy is the ability to utilise information and communication technologies to find, comprehend, evaluate, produce, and convey information (ALA's Literacy Clearinghouse, 2017). In the same way, we can define digital literacy as the capacity to use a variety of digital devices to effectively and critically navigate, assess and produce information (European commission, 2017). Digital literacy is defined as the capacity to efficiently access, manage, and assess information using digital technology, communication tools, and networks. For Nigerian university students, this includes a variety of abilities such as using word processors and spreadsheets, navigating online research resources, comprehending cybersecurity, and engaging in social media platforms for academic purposes. As students rely more on digital technologies for study, communication, and collaboration, digital literacy becomes critical to their success in today's academic environment. It is no longer enough to have basic computer abilities; students must be able to use digital resources to support their academic work and interact with the larger global knowledge network.

Digital literacy has changed learning paradigm in the universities through the integration of digital technologies in education (Simpson & Obdalova, 2014). It has made the practice and promotion of digital literacy in the universities indispensable and an essential responsibility of the universities. The presence of digital technologies in the Nigeria universities has increased the need for students to become digitally literate. This form of literacy not only empowers students on the use of digital technologies but to take proper advantage of the positive outcomes of digital tools (Njenga, 2018)

In today's technologically driven academic atmosphere, university students must be digitally literate. Access to online resources, research journals, e-books, and educational platforms improves educational quality and promotes self-directed learning. In Nigerian colleges, where traditional teaching techniques may be limited, digital literacy allows students to complement their learning with extensive internet resources. Furthermore, it prepares them for the needs of the workplace, where technological skill is increasingly required. A digitally literate learner is more prepared to collaborate, solve problems with digital tools, and adjust to future technology needs. Digital literacy is very important in the school environment because it enhances the use of information in appropriate ways and creates new ideas and products collaboratively. This is why Universities students must possess specific skills to effectively navigate embedded resources such as hyperlinks, audio clips, graphs or charts. This includes the ability to critically evaluate the reliability and credibility of online sources, interpret data presented in various formats and synthesized information from different media. Thus, students who use both cognitive and technical skills to find, evaluate, create and communicate information are on their way to becoming digitally literate. Beethan and Sharper (2019) supported the idea that digital literacy does not only encompasses technical skills but also critical thinking, problem-solving and ability to evaluate information sources critically. Similarly, Mundy and Kuprite (2019) says that digital literacy is not merely about technical skills but also encompasses the cognitive social and emotional competencies required to navigate the digital landscape effectively. On the other hand, critical thinking is vital skills that enable individuals to analyze information, make informed decisions,

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and solve complex problems. Hence, Ennis (2015) highlighted the importance of critical thinking as an essential skill for individuals to make sound decisions and solve complex problem.

Also, research conducted by scholars like Onyedike and Okonkwo (2019) emphasized the position of correlation between digital literacy and critical thinking skills among universities students. The researchers found that students who were proficient in using digital tools and resources were more likely to demonstrate higher level of critical thinking abilities. Similarly, Adejumo et al, (2018) emphasized the importance of integrating digital literacy into the curriculum to enhance critical thinking skills among students. Hence, the relationship between digital literacy and critical thinking has been a topic of interest in educational research, with studies indicating that proficiency in digital tools can enhance students' critical thinking abilities (Wang, 2021, Green and Hannon, 2017). Thus, despite the importance of digital literacy in fostering critical thinking, many students face challenges in both areas. This is why, Alao (2021) opined that even when students have access to digital technologies, they often lack the necessary skills to use these tools effectively. As a result, there is rising worry that poor digital literacy training may impede students' ability to engage in critical thinking, affecting their academic achievement and preparation for workplace in the large society. Furthermore, the integration of digital technology in teaching and learning at Nigerian universities may present issues for students who do not have access to digital application tools, thus affecting their critical thinking skills. As a result, given Nigeria's distinct socioeconomic and educational backdrop, is there inadequate empirical evidence in studying the relationships between digital literacy and critical thinking among university students in Nigeria. In this situation, the university failed to meet their student learning need in the area of digital literacy. Based on this background, the researchers intended to investigate digital literacy and its correlation with critical thinking among students in Delta State University Abraka

Statement of the Research Problem

Even though digital literacy is crucial for developing critical thinking abilities, many Nigerian students, particularly those at Delta State University, Abraka, continue to struggle in both areas. According to research in these fields, students frequently lack the abilities needed to use digital technologies efficiently, even when they have access to them (Alao, 2021). Furthermore, there is rising concern that students' academic performance and preparedness for the workforce may suffer if they receive insufficient instruction in digital literacy, which could impair their capacity for critical thought. This circumstance bothers the researcher because the study's question is: How do students at Delta State University Abraka relate to digital literacy and critical thinking?

Purpose of the study

The overall objective of this study is to examine the relationship between digital literacy and critical thinking among students in Delta State University Abraka. Specifically, the paper sought to:

1. Investigate the relationship between digital literacy and critical thinking among students in Delta State University Abraka.

Research Question

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One research question was slated to guide the study.

1. What is the relationship between digital literacy and critical thinking among students in Delta State University Abraka?

Hypothesis

A null hypothesis was formulated for the study

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between digital literacy and critical thinking among students in Delta State University Abraka.

Methodology

The study adopted a correlational research design. Correlational research design according to Nwogu (2015), is a type of research design used to determine the extent to which two or more variables are related. This design involves measuring and analyzing the relationship between variables but does not imply causation. In correlation research, the focus is on determining the strength and direction of the relationship between variables rather than establishing a cause-and-effect relationship. Thus, the design was adopted in investigating digital literacy and its correlation with critical thinking among students. The population of the study is 1,020 students comprises of Computer Science Education and Business Education Department of Delta State University Abraka. The sample size of the study was 102 students of Delta State University, Abraka. Ten percent (10%) of the entire number of students was taken according to Keiligner's recommendation that a study sample element should make up of (10%) of the entire population. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire tagged Digital Literacy and correlation on Critical Thinking among students of University (DLCCTASUA). The questionnaire was made of 20 items which was divided into two parts. Part A consisted of personal data while part B consisted of the 20 items. The items were placed on four (4) points rating scale Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD). The instrument was face validated by two experts at the Delta State University, Delta State Nigeria. The Cronbach Alpha reliability was used to determine the consistency of the instrument which provided reliability co-efficient of 0.98. Mean and standard deviation was used to analyze the research question for the study at 2.50. Indicating that if the calculated mean value is more than 2.50, it is accepted but if it is less than the 2.50, it is rejected. Regression was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05. significant level. Indicating that if the observed p-value is less than the fixed p-value, accept otherwise reject.

Research Question One: What is the relationship between digital literacy and critical thinking skills among students in Delta State University Abraka?

To answer this research question, responses obtained from the respondents were coded and subjected to descriptive statistics of Mean (\bar{x}), Standard Deviation (SD), Correlation (r)

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Table 1: Respondents’ Mean Score, Standard Deviation and Correlation between Digital Literacy and Critical Thinking among Students in Delta State University Abraka.

Variable	N	\bar{x}	SD	r	Remarks
Digital Literacy	102	25.24	3.675	0.145	Positive weak Relationship
Critical Thinking	102	25.00	3.599		

The results in Table 1. show that students’ digital literacy means and standard deviation scores was 25.24 & 3.675, respectively. Thus, the mean score of 25.24 indicates positive weak relationship among students and the standard deviation of 3.675 indicates weak relationship in students’ digital literacy. Also, the results show that mean and standard deviation scores of Critical Thinking are (25.00 & 3.599). The mean score of 25.00 reflects a weak relationship and the standard deviation of 3.599 shows a considerable weak relationship, indicating differences in critical thinking among students of Delta State University Abraka. The correlation coefficient of $r=0.145$ indicates a weak relationship between digital literacy and critical thinking among students in Delta State University Abraka. This implies that digital literacy scores do not contribute to critical thinking scores of students.

Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between digital literacy and critical thinking skill among students in Delta State University Abraka

To test the hypothesis, Simple Linear Regression was computed, with scores on Digital Literacy as an independent variable and Critical Thinking as the dependent variable. The students’ scores of digital literacies were converted from the frequency of responses into a continuous scale. The result of the Simple Regression analysis of relationship between digital literacy and critical thinking is shown in the SPSS output in Table2.

Table 2: Model Summary on Simple Regression Analysis of Relationship between Digital Literacy and Critical Thinking among Students in Delta State University Abraka

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.145 ^a	.021	.011	3.578

a. Predictors: (Constant), Digital Literacy

The model in Table 2. revealed that $r=3.578$ which shows a positive weak relationship between digital literacy and critical thinking, suggesting that digital literacy does not increases critical thinking, may slightly improve, but the relationship is not strong. The adjusted R square ($R^2 = 0.011$) indicates that digital literacy could contribute 1.1% to critical thinking among students in Delta State University Abraka. Further to the above revelations, and in order to determine whether digital literacy was a

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significant predictor of critical thinking, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was computed as presented in Table 3.

Table 3: ANOVA for Regression Analysis of Relationship between Digital Literacy and Critical Thinking among Students of Delta State University Abraka

	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	27.585	1	27.585	2.154	.145 ^b
	Residual	1280.415	100	12.804		
	Total	1308.00	101			

a. Dependent Variable: Critical Thinking

b. Predictors: (Constant), Digital Literacy

From Table 3, it was evident that digital literacy was a significant predictor of critical thinking [$F(1,100)=2.154, p=.145 < 0.05$]. Since the p -value of 0.145 is greater than the alpha value of 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis which stated that “There is no significant relationship between Digital Literacy and Critical thinking among students in Delta State University Abraka” is accepted. Indicating that there was a statistically significant positive weak relationship between digital literacy and critical thinking among students in Delta State University Abraka. This result further implies that digital literacy is a causative agent of critical thinking. Further, still, to the above findings, linear regression was generated to find the actual influence of digital literacy on critical thinking. Hence, the need to interpret the regression coefficient as shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Regression Coefficient for Digital Literacy and Critical Thinking among Students of Delta State University Abraka :

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	21.412	2.470		8.668	.000
	Digital Literacy	.142	.097	.145	1.468	.145

a. Dependent Variable: Critical Thinking

Table 4. shows that the regression equation for digital literacy and critical thinking among students of Delta State University Abraka scores is $y=21.412+ X=0.142$ for digital literacy scores. This indicates that for every 1-point decrease in digital literacy score, there is a decrease of critical thinking score by 0.142 units on average. Therefore, the overall regression coefficient was found that digital literacy does not statistically predict critical thinking $B=0.145, t=1.468, p=0.145 < 0.05$ respectively. This implies that digital literacy does not have a significant impact on critical thinking among students in Delta State University Abraka.

Discussion of Finding

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The study was designed to investigate digital literacy and its correlation with critical thinking among students of delta state university Abraka. One research question and one hypothesis were stated to the relationship between the variables of interest in the study.

Analysis based on Research Question one, as presented in Table 1, the results in Table 1. shows that students' digital literacy mean and standard deviation scores was 25.24 & 3.675 Thus, the mean score of 25.24 indicates positive weak relationship among students and the standard deviation of 3.675 indicates positive weak relationship in students' digital literacy. Also, the results show that mean and standard deviation scores of Critical Thinking were 25.00 & 3.599. The mean score of 25.00 reflects a positive weak relationship and the standard deviation of 3.599 shows a considerable positive weak relationship, indicating differences in critical thinking among students of Delta State University Abraka. The correlation coefficient of $r=0.145$ indicates a positive weak relationship between digital literacy and critical thinking among students in Delta State University Abraka. This implies that higher digital literacy scores are associated with higher critical thinking scores of students. Thus, students with higher digital literacy abilities tend to have higher critical thinking

The hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between digital literacy and critical thinking among students in Delta State University Abraka. This hypothesis was confirmed. This present finding was in line with Alao, (2021) opined that even when students have access to digital technologies, they often lack the necessary skills to use these tools effectively. Similarly, European commission (2013) emphasized that there is consistent with literature that many students who enter higher education have no digital literacy needed for digital learning. Scholars like Prior et al, (2016) cited in Anthonysamy (2020) further explained that students are proactive in using technology for social media or entertainment but not for learning. In contrary, Beethan and Sharper, (2019) argued that digital literacy is not only encompasses technical skills but also critical thinking, problem-solving and ability to evaluate information sources critically. Furthermore, Mundy and Kuprite, (2019) says that digital literacy is not merely about technical skills but also encompasses the cognitive social and emotional competencies required to navigate the digital landscape effectively

Conclusion

The analysis shows that there is a weak and statistically non-significant relationship between digital literacy and critical thinking among students in Delta State, Nigeria. While there is a slight positive correlation, digital literacy does not meaningfully explain variations in critical thinking. Other factors may have a stronger influence on critical thinking and should be explored in future studies.

Recommendations

1. universities should teach students on the use digital in learning.

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